

IMPACT OF HOLISTIC MARKETING PHILOSOPHY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN RETAIL BANKING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN KERALA

A Report

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POSTDOCTORALFELLOW

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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SYNOPSIS OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH WORK IMPACT OF HOLISTIC MARKETING PHILOSOPHY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN RETAIL BANKING, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN KERALA.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of the retail banking sector, the pursuit of customer loyalty stands as an evergreen quest. Banking institutions worldwide are confronted with the challenge of not only attracting but also retaining customers in an environment characterized by increasing competition, evolving customer preferences, and digital transformation. The province of Kerala, known for its rich cultural heritage and distinct socio-economic dynamics, presents a particularly intriguing context for this exploration.

Public sector banks in Kerala, as staunch pillars of financial inclusion and economic development, have played a pivotal role in serving the diverse needs of the state's populace. However, their journey towards nurturing customer loyalty in this age of heightened expectations requires a profound shift in perspective. This shift finds its resonance in the holistic marketing philosophy, an approach that recognizes the interconnectedness of all marketing elements and their collective influence on customer experiences.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The impact of holistic marketing on customer loyalty in the context of retail banking sector is a widely discussed topic in the literature. This section targets popular journals, magazines and various text books that contain fruitful information on holistic marketing and its dimensions as well as customer loyalty and retail banking.

Holistic Marketing

According to Govindarajan (2007), the concept of holistic marketing entails the wider view of marketing strategies that involve the development of marketing programs, processes and activities that help in the marketing of products. He points out that the concept of holistic marketing plays an important role, especially in selecting marketing formats that help in identification of comfortable marketing strategies. He states that the concept of holistic marketing is based on four major components that enable effective designing and implementing of marketing programs and processes. These holistic marketing components include effective relationship marketing, the integrated and internal marketing, and, furthermore, the performance marketing as they are essential for effective marketing strategies.

Customer loyalty

Creating a strong, tight connection to customers is the dream of any banks and often the key to long-term marketing success. Banks that want to form such bonds should heed some specific considerations. The Kotler and Keller (2012) explain four types of marketing activities companies are using to improve loyalty and retention 1).Interacting with customers, 2).Developing loyalty programs 3). Personalizing marketing and 4). Creating institutional ties.

Retail Banking

Dr.R.Srinivasa Rao (2014) explained that Retail banking is when a bank executes transactions directly with consumers, rather than corporations or other banks. Services offered include savings and transactional accounts, mortgages, personal loans, debit cards, and cards. Today, retail banking is being considered as one of the most innovative financial services provided by the various commercial Public Sector Banks (PSBs), private sector and foreign banks. Retail banking has a huge potential considering the growing demand for its products namely, term deposits, consumer durable loans, auto loans, debit card, credit cards, ATM facilities, insurance, online banking, etc.

The aforesaid review of literature reveals that impact of holistic marketing concept on customer loyalty in retail banking of public sector banks have not been studied extensively in India. Further coming to Kerala, it is implicit that there is no systematic and detailed studies in this respect have not been conducted. In this context, it is highly imperative to have an in depth study regarding the holistic marketing practices of public sector banks in Kerala. This study aims to fill up the research gap by examining customers loyalty towards holistic marketing practices of public sector banks on the basis of following dimensions viz. relationship marketing, internal marketing, integrated marketing and performance marketing.

On the basis of above literature review, following research framework is developed.

Figure 1 – Research Framework

3. IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Everything matters under the holistic marketing umbrella. In a developing economy, product and service offerings have multiplied exponentially along with competition. Information is available instantly. The new marketing paradigm has shifted the emphasis from product and production, to selling, then integrated marketing within the holistic marketing concept. The study helps to describes and analyses the ways in which holistic marketing can assist banks to connect with customers. It also explains how holistic marketing can help in building brands. Moreover, the study explains how holistic marketing can deliver and communicate value. Holistic marketing helps to provide a seamless customer interactions process that ensures the customers to get the level of service they expect. More than that holistic marketing helps banks to boost their business efficiency, thereby increasing profit and revenue generations capabilities.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The purpose of the study is to provide a deeper understanding of how holistic marketing concept helps the organizations to create and maintain customer loyalty. From the problem discussion researcher has formulated the following research questions.

1. How holistic marketing philosophy helps the public sector banks to achieve the customer loyalty in Kerala?
2. Which holistic marketing dimensions are essential in forming loyalty among Kerala customers in association with retail banking?

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The overall objective is to evaluate the impact of holistic marketing on customer loyalty in the public sectors in Kerala.

1. To examine how relationship marketing, internal marketing, integrated marketing and performance marketing affect on customer loyalty in Kerala's public sector banks.
2. To determine the benefits of these partnerships and the interactions between holistic marketing and customer loyalty in the public sector banks.

6. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1: There may have significant positive relationship between internal marketing and customer loyalty.

H2: There may have significant positive relationship between integrated marketing and customer loyalty.

H3: There may have significant positive relationship between performance marketing and customer loyalty.

H4: There may have significant positive relationship between relationship marketing and customer loyalty.

H5: Holistic marketing may have high influence on customer loyalty.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study will be mainly used descriptive and analytical research designs to measure the impact of holistic marketing on customer loyalty. In this study all the retail customers who utilize the retail service offered by the various types of public sector banks in Kerala is the population for the study. Simple random sampling method will be adopted to collect primary data using the structured questionnaire. The questionnaire in this study plans to design a closed – end questions where the respondents have to make their response in a 5 point Likert scale varying from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree”. To understand the demographic profile of the respondents, questions related to Age, Sex, Qualification and Income etc are includes. For analyzing the data both simple and advanced statistical tools will be used. Statistical tools like average, Mean, Standard Deviation, Reliability analysis, ANOVA, Correlation analysis, Multiple Regression analysis, Multicollinearity test and SEM analysis etc plan to use.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

In the current landscape of economic uncertainty, the importance of delivering an exceptional banking experience, tailored to each individual, is more pronounced than ever (Feyen, E., et al. (2021) [1]). As highlighted by Purcărea and Rațiu (2009) [2]), banking customer service experts have noted that those banks actively cultivating customer loyalty through exceptional service find themselves partially insulated against economic downturns. During challenging times, customers gravitate toward banks that genuinely prioritize their well-being, emphasizing the significance of a caring approach (Maechler, N., et al. (2021) [3]). As Belding (2008) [4] pointed out, individuals become more discerning about how and where they allocate their financial resources. Banks that have a history of mistreating, neglecting, or mishandling their customers are particularly vulnerable during economic downturns (Lichtenberg, P.A. (2016) [5]). Therefore, customer loyalty has a direct impact on how customers perceive a bank in comparison to its competitors (Chinedu, P.A., et al. (2020)[6]). The loyalty of customer's hold of banking services is intricately tied to their experiences during financial transactions and the overall retail banking process (Gerard D.T., et al. (2018)[7]). Customer loyalty profoundly influences the mental positioning of a bank among competitive alternatives (Mukhiddin J., et al. (2012) [8]). A customer-centric approach allows banks to gauge the effectiveness of their efforts in meeting customer needs and expectations (Deninzon D., et al. (2019) [9]). This alignment hinges on the collection and efficient utilization of robust customer data (Macdonald S., (2023) [10]). Customers also value how banks and their partners address dissatisfaction, inefficiency, and opportunities (Divya I., et al. (2023) [11]). This underscores the importance of not only providing a seamless banking experience but also effectively managing issues and leveraging opportunities for improvement (Thomas R., (2021) [12]).

Today's retail banking experience is marked by its intricate nature, making the task of discerning the determinants of customer loyalty more challenging (Severoni Elisabetta (2022) [13]). With an ever-evolving landscape, the ways in which customers can engage with their banks have increased significantly compared to just a few years ago (Paul S., et al. (2022) [14]). Numerous variables, such as one's location, the urgency they feel, or the specific service they are after, can influence their banking channel preference (Shital C., et al. (2019) [15]). Consequently, what constitutes an ideal customer experience varies based on the individual, the service, and the medium (Lassignardie J., et al., (2013) [16]). The Global Banking Voice of the Customer Survey from 2013 indicated that the quality of banking services plays a more pivotal role in swaying customer choices in emerging markets compared to established ones (Nittala N., (2021) [17]). This suggests that by enhancing their customer loyalty initiatives, banks in emerging markets can carve out a distinctive edge over their competitors (Rakhi T., (2014) [18]).

Since India gained its independence, its banking sector has witnessed transformative changes. Particularly notable was the shift during the 1990s with economic liberalization and the government's move to reduce its stake in banks, echoing the recommendations of the Narasimham committee. These reforms presented challenges for the Indian banking industry (Sriram, M.S. (2019) [19]). Amidst these competitive and demanding times, maintaining a devoted customer base has become paramount for banks (Haitham A.A. (2015) [20]). To achieve this and bolster their market standing and profitability, Indian banks must strategize to enhance customer satisfaction (Jitender K., et al., (2023) [21]).

Holistic marketing emphasizes the notion that every touch point, accessible from anywhere and anytime, plays a pivotal role in shaping the service experience in retail banking (Ann B. (2019) [22]). It's a comprehensive approach that considers the entirety of the banking business. When employing this approach, banks meticulously evaluate all interactions, be it through their products, online platforms, promotional materials, or otherwise (Amarnath H. (2022) [23]). This perspective on marketing not only offers a broad view of the consumer journey but also sheds light on how customer value is captured (Nikita D. (2022) [24]). At its core, holistic marketing aims to foster long-lasting, mutually beneficial relationships by seamlessly intertwining value exploration, creation, and delivery. One of the main pillars of holistic marketing is consistent communication. The objective is to convey a consistent message to the intended audience, ensuring that every customer interaction reinforces the same message. Such consistency can bolster customer trust and loyalty, further elevating the brand's reputation (Juliana M. (2022) [25]). With this context in mind, the researcher seeks to delve into "IMPACT OF HOLISTIC MARKETING PHILOSOPHY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN RETAIL BANKING, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS IN KERALA" to understand its role in enhancing customer loyalty, boosting retention, streamlining sales and services, increasing revenue, and attracting new clientele.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In the contemporary, fiercely competitive banking environment, especially in distinct regions like Kerala with its special socio-cultural attributes, the goal for public banks extends beyond mere customer acquisition to fostering long-term loyalty (Bindu K.N., et al., (2019) [26]). Marketing dynamics have evolved, transitioning from product-centric to customer-centric, now merging into an all-encompassing holistic marketing perspective. This research offers vital strategies highlighting how embracing a holistic marketing lens can redefine customer loyalty, providing public banks with strategies to thrive in this complex environment (Mirko S. (2023) [27]). Given their historical significance and widespread network, public sector banks in Kerala need to adapt swiftly to ever-changing consumer desires. The research emphasizes how a unified marketing strategy can refine bank operations, enhance customer touchpoints, and foster deeper relationships. By dissecting the transformative effect of holistic marketing on customer allegiance, banks can pinpoint elements that align closely with their customer's values, subsequently refining their services for better alignment. For these banks, a reputation of reliability and excellence is essential (Nunung A.S. (2023) [28]). This research underscores how an integrated marketing approach can amplify customer trust, fortifying the bank's image.

As foundational pillars in Kerala's socio-economic structure, public banks have a larger role to play. Boosted loyalty signifies growth for the banks and overall economic health for the region. By underscoring the criticality of a comprehensive marketing strategy, this research offers actionable insights for these institutions, ensuring they remain dependable anchors for the local population. The insights derived from this study can inform banking strategies and policy-making. By comprehending the intricate interplay between integrated marketing and customer loyalty, banks can devise policies, training modules, and initiatives that resonate with holistic marketing principles (Abdulazeez A.S., et al., (2023) [29]). At its core, this research's value lies in its potential to recalibrate the strategic directives of Kerala's public sector banks. By elucidating the symbiotic link between integrated marketing practices and sustained customer loyalty, it paves the way for these banks to elevate their significance, influence, and accomplishments in today's banking milieu.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

The banking landscape worldwide is undergoing a significant metamorphosis, driven by technological leaps, shifting customer preferences, and heightened competitive pressures. In this evolving scenario, public banks in Kerala, characterized by its distinct socio-cultural nuances, grapple with the task of nurturing enduring customer loyalty. In contemporary banking, loyalty isn't just an outcome of monetary transactions but is deeply rooted in the comprehensive

experience and value presented to consumers.

Enter holistic marketing, an approach emphasizing the synergy of all business facets to offer unmatched customer value. By integrating diverse business aspects, holistic marketing offers a more cohesive and inclusive approach to attracting and retaining customers. This study aims to investigate the impact of this comprehensive marketing perspective on banks' capacities to foster lasting customer loyalty. From this core objective, two primary research inquiries emerge:

1. How does embracing a holistic marketing perspective empower Kerala's public banks to enhance and maintain customer loyalty?
2. Among the varied dimensions of holistic marketing, which are most influential in determining customer loyalty within Kerala's public banking sector in the realm of retail banking?

The inaugural query ventures into understanding how the holistic marketing paradigm can be the cornerstone in amplifying loyalty in Kerala's banking domain. The subsequent question delves into the multifaceted realm of holistic marketing. Given its diverse components – from relationship and internal marketing to integrated and performance marketing – it's essential to discern which aspects resonate most within Kerala's unique banking clientele and how they shape loyalty dynamics.

In essence, these research queries aim to unravel the nuanced relationship between comprehensive marketing techniques and customer loyalty, set against the rich backdrop of Kerala's banking sector. This research endeavor hopes to unearth insights and strategies that can propel Kerala's public banks towards sustained customer allegiance in this transformative epoch.

OBJECTIVES

The primary aim of this research is to assess the ramifications of holistic marketing strategies on customer loyalty within the retail banking realm of Kerala. Expanding upon this, the study will delve into the following objectives:

1. To scrutinize how facets of holistic marketing, including relationship marketing, internal marketing, integrated marketing, and performance marketing, sway customer loyalty in Kerala's retail banking sector.
2. To discern the intricate connections between holistic marketing practices and the loyalty of customers, shedding light on the advantages that emerge from these interrelations.
3. To prove the conceptual model empirically by testing the hypotheses.
4. To understand any potential barriers or challenges retail banks in Kerala face in effectively integrating holistic marketing strategies, and how these may affect customer loyalty.
5. To evaluate the final conceptual model developed using empirical study.

6. To analyze the conceptual model developed using ABCD analysis framework.
7. To propose actionable insights and recommendations for banks to optimize their holistic marketing approaches, thereby augmenting customer loyalty.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Holistic marketing in the banking industry is a comprehensive approach that recognizes the interconnectedness of various marketing activities. It plays a critical role in fostering customer loyalty and ensuring sustained business growth, particularly in an industry where trust and long-term relationships are paramount (Magdolen, R.(2010) [30]). The first key element is Relationship Marketing, which prioritizes the cultivation of enduring customer relationships rather than transient transactions. For banks, this involves gaining a deep understanding of customer needs throughout their lifetimes, offering personalized services, and maintaining consistent communication. The goal is to make customers feel valued, ultimately earning their unwavering trust and loyalty (Patwardhan, A.M. (2014 [31]). The second component, Integrated Marketing, focuses on maintaining a consistent brand message across all channels, spanning physical branches and online platforms. In today's digital era, a bank customer may interact with the institution through a branch visit, mobile app usage, and customer service calls in a single day. Integrated marketing ensures a seamless and uniform experience across these touch points. Internal Marketing, the third component, regards employees as internal customers, recognizing their pivotal role in shaping the customer experience (Wijaya W.S. & et.al.(20110[32]). Frontline staff, whether at the teller counter or on the phone, directly influence how customers perceive the bank. Ensuring that these employees are aligned with the bank's mission and values is of utmost importance. The final component, Performance Marketing, enables banks to gauge the effectiveness of their campaigns by measuring customer engagement and acquisition directly. Given the increasing shift of banking services to the online realm, this results-driven approach ensures adaptability, allowing banks to swiftly respond to evolving customer behaviors and market dynamics (Pongklee, A. & Pawapootanont, S. (2011) [33]).

Holistic marketing is an indispensable factor in strengthening customer loyalty in the banking industry, where trust and enduring relationships are paramount. The four core principles of this approach collaborate to establish and nurture customer loyalty effectively (Pop, N.A. & et. al. (2012) [34]). To begin, Relationship Marketing transcends mere transactions and focuses on building enduring connections with customers. Banks can foster these relationships by comprehending their evolving needs and personalizing services, creating a deep-seated trust between customers and the bank as a trusted partner in their financial journey. In today's world of multichannel interactions, from physical branches to mobile apps, Integrated Marketing ensures a seamless and uniform experience, further enhancing the bank's image of reliability (Nigam, A.

(2011[35]). On the internal front, Internal Marketing recognizes the crucial role played by bank employees in shaping the customer experience. Aligning employees with the bank's mission and vision guarantees consistent, high-quality service for customers (Zaman, K. & et.al. (2012[36])). In our digitized age, Performance Marketing empowers banks to respond swiftly to customer preferences and needs. By tailoring services based on real-time feedback and data-driven insights, banks show their commitment to delivering exceptional value, thereby deepening customer loyalty (Tushi, T.E., (2014[37])).

Based on thorough research and a deep dive into existing literature, this study proposes five fundamental hypotheses. These are designed to identify the key factors that influence the connection between holistic marketing and customer loyalty in the banking sector.

Postulate 1: Internal marketing strategies, which align and motivate employees to deliver consistent and high-quality service, inherently influence how customers perceive and engage with a banking institution.

Postulate 2: Every touch point in a customer's journey, whether offline or online, contributes to their overall perception and experience with a bank.

Postulate 3: Quantifiable outcomes from specific marketing activities directly reflect the effectiveness of these activities in influencing customer behavior.

Postulate 4: Sustained and meaningful interactions fostered by institutions, over time, cultivate deeper bonds of trust and loyalty with customers.

Postulate 5: A comprehensive approach to marketing, which integrates various facets seamlessly, offers superior value and experience to customers, thereby influencing their loyalty.

Based on the previously mentioned postulates, a conceptual model was developed to examine the study's key factors. This framework integrates the essential aspects of holistic marketing and their correlation with customer loyalty. As a result of this study, a suggested a conceptual model is presented (Figure 1).

Figure 1.1: Proposed Conceptual Model

HYPOTHESES

In the dynamic world of the banking industry, customer loyalty remains an elusive yet crucial metric, directly impacting a bank's long-term profitability and market share. As markets evolve and consumer preferences shift, understanding the determinants of customer loyalty becomes essential. Holistic marketing, with its broad and interconnected perspective on marketing activities, emerges as a potent lens to understand this. This approach not only emphasizes individual marketing strategies but also the synergy between them, aiming to provide consistent value to customers. Recognizing the intricate relationship between marketing strategies and customer loyalty, this study embarks on an exploration of the multifaceted realm of holistic marketing. The study posits five distinct hypotheses, each delving into a specific dimension of marketing, in order to unravel the underlying mechanisms influencing customer loyalty within the banking industry.

H1: The extent of customer loyalty is significantly determined by the effectiveness of internal marketing strategies.

H2: The level of loyalty among customers is markedly influenced by the application of integrated marketing techniques.

H3: There exists a significant correlation between the outcomes of performance marketing initiatives and the degree of customer loyalty.

H4: The depth of customer loyalty is substantially affected by the methodologies employed in relationship marketing.

H5: The overarching practices of holistic marketing play a pivotal role in shaping the magnitude

of customer loyalty.

CONCEPTUAL & OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

➤ Holistic Marketing

Holistic marketing emphasizes the idea that 'every aspect is crucial' in marketing, requiring a comprehensive and cohesive perspective to achieve the optimal solution. This contemporary marketing approach effectively and efficiently leverages its four components (Internal marketing, integrated marketing, relationship marketing, and performance marketing) to meet the objectives of Public Sector Banks.

➤ Relationship Marketing

This approach focuses on building and maintaining lasting relationships with clients to secure and sustain their banking engagements.

➤ Internal Marketing

It refers to the practice of treating bank employees as internal customers and ensuring their needs, motivations, and satisfaction are addressed effectively. It is a strategic approach that recognizes the significance of a bank's staff in delivering quality customer service and achieving bank goals.

➤ Integrated Marketing

This strategy encompasses the blending of multiple facets of banking operations and services to ensure a consistent and unified brand message and customer experience.

➤ Performance Marketing

Performance marketing examines various banking tasks, such as product sales strategies, brand equity, customer value, as well as the ethical and legal standards that a business and its products must maintain.

➤ Retail Banking

Retail banking, often simply referred to as personal banking, refers to the provision of financial services to individual consumers rather than to companies or other banks. It offers a suite of standard services including savings accounts, current accounts, fixed deposits, recurring deposits, and personal loans.

➤ Customer Loyalty

It refers to the consistent preference and commitment of a customer towards a particular bank's services and products, even when presented with alternatives from competing institutions.

METHODOLOGY

This study primarily employed a descriptive and analytical research design to assess the influence of holistic marketing on customer loyalty. The research focused on retail banking customers in Kerala. The investigation was conducted at major public sector banks in Kerala, including the State Bank of India, Canara Bank, Union Bank of India, Bank of Baroda, Punjab National Bank, and Indian Overseas Bank. The study considered individuals holding savings and current accounts with these six major banks as potential participants. A sample of 150 respondents from retail banking customers was selected using a simple random sampling method to ensure representation.

The study collected primary data through a pretested questionnaire, which had undergone modifications based on feedback from a pilot study. Data collection for this research took place from March 2023 to May 2023. The questionnaire comprised two parts. The first part collected general information from respondents, including their name, gender, age, marital status, occupation, qualifications, bank name, account type, and monthly income. The second part of the questionnaire consisted of 25 items categorized into five dimensions. The first four dimensions are "Relationship Marketing," "Integrated Marketing," "Internal Marketing," and "Performance Marketing," and the fifth dimension, "Customer Loyalty,.". The Likert scale with five-point ratings ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" was utilized for respondents to express their opinions.

TOOLS OF ANALYSIS

Mean, Standard Deviation, Reliability Analysis, Correlation analysis, Multiple Regression analysis, Multicollinearity test and SEM analysis was used for analyzing whether each holistic marketing dimension is influenced on customer loyalty.

VARIABLES USED FOR THE STUDY

Independent Variables

- a) Relationship marketing
- b) Internal marketing
- c) Integrated marketing
- d) Performance Marketing

Dependent Variables

- e) Customer loyalty

LIMITATION OF STUDY

The following limitations were faced during the research was carried out:

- Participants responded to the survey based on their personal knowledge, which might not accurately reflect the actual situation.
- Due to confidentiality and security concerns, banks were reluctant to share specific customer data, posing challenges during sample design and selection.
- Most of the information essential for this study was qualitative, gathered using a five-point scale. Therefore, the inherent limitations of such scaling methods influenced the results of this study.

PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY

1. Chapter 1 narrates the significance, research problem, objectives, research methodology, various tools and limitation of the study.
2. Chapter 2 deals with the review of earlier studies.
3. Chapter 3 deals with analysis and interpretation.
4. Chapter 4 narrates the findings conclusion and suggestions.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF EARLIER STUDIES

The influence of holistic marketing on customer loyalty within the retail banking sector is a frequently explored subject in the existing literature. In this section, the focus is on authoritative journals, informative magazines, and diverse textbooks that provide valuable insights regarding holistic marketing, its components, as well as the dynamics of customer loyalty and its application in retail banking.

Holistic Marketing

Holistic marketing addresses a change in outlook in marketing philosophy. Kotler P., et al. ((2002)[38]) presented this idea as a structure that coordinates different marketing activities, emphasizing customer relationships, societal well-being, and environmental sustainability. It urges organizations to consider the whole worth chain, from item plan to post-buy client service. The holistic marketing strategy is an expansive term that alludes to an organization's program of distinguishing a particular market division and attempting to fulfill that division involving marketing mix elements in the most potential compelling manner (Ali, et al., (2015) [39]). As indicated by Kotler P., et al. (2009[40]), holistic marketing is the business thinking of the twenty-first century. It depends on the turn of events, plan, and execution of marketing activities and and cycles that perceive the degree and expansiveness of their association. As per Ali (2015), a more exhaustive and strong way to deal with business direction is expected for the 21st century firm than the conventional application. As per them, the holistic marketing idea perceives that all that in promoting matters. Thus, the concept of holistic marketing is rooted in the notion that a comprehensive marketing strategy should encompass all facets of marketing. Holistic marketing includes various dimensions such as internal marketing, performance marketing, integrated marketing, and relationship marketing. By thoroughly assessing the target market and devising an appropriate marketing plan, this holistic marketing approach outlines the organization's strategy for effectively reaching and engaging with the customer. (Al-Bakri, et al., (2014) [41]). The development of the holistic marketing idea at the turn of the third thousand years, as indicated by Pop. et al., (2012[42]), represented another test in marketing theory and practice. Holistic marketing is defined by Kotler P., et al. ((2002)[43]) as the turn of events, plan, and execution of promoting projects, tasks, and exercises to survey their generally and covering influence. It's likewise a critical system for accomplishing joining with regards to quality administration and adjusted execution (Tejedor et. al. 2014)[44]). According to Govindarajan (2007)[45]), holistic marketing embraces a broad perspective on marketing strategies,

encompassing the creation of marketing programs, processes, and activities that facilitate the promotion of products. It emphasizes the significance of this approach in choosing marketing formats that aid in the identification of effective marketing strategies.

How Holistic Marketing Connects Banks with its Customers

The paper delves into a comprehensive examination of the four primary components of holistic marketing, shedding light on how holistic marketing serves as a bridge between banks and their customers. Holistic marketing involves the formulation and execution of marketing programs and processes that facilitate the cultivation of marketing relationships. One of the core components within holistic marketing is integrated marketing, which has proven instrumental in establishing connections between organizations and their customer base. Integrated marketing empowers organizations to efficiently and seamlessly convey vital business information to their customers. It's worth noting that holistic marketing incorporates marketing programs that are not only cost-effective but also highly effective in delivering valuable information to customers (Gandhi R. (2015)[46]).

Internal marketing is a pivotal component of holistic marketing, playing a crucial role in facilitating organizations' connections with their customers. It primarily focuses on training and motivating an organization's employees to effectively serve customers. In this context, many banks foster the formation of business groups that empower their employees to address customer service needs efficiently. This approach has notably strengthened the connection between banks and their customers. Internal marketing operates at two distinct levels to foster organizations' connections with customers. Firstly, it ensures that all marketing functions, spanning from market research to advertising, are meticulously developed and harmonized through a collaborative and cohesive working environment among employees. Secondly, it emphasizes active involvement from various functional departments, promoting effective collaboration and coordination to meet marketing objectives. These two levels of internal marketing enable stakeholders, including employees, to devise marketing concepts that cater to customer needs and, consequently, enhance the organization's engagement with its customers (Himansu, S. M. (2009)[47]). On a related note, the role of social responsibility marketing as a holistic marketing concept in forging connections between organizations and their customers. She highlights that an organization's social responsibility in marketing signifies not only its capacity to sell products but also its commitment to social concerns, particularly within its immediate environment. The holistic marketing concept has empowered organizations to adopt marketing strategies that prioritize social responsibility, thereby enhancing their product marketing and strengthening their connections with customers (Noked, N. (2011) [48]). In their study, Singh & Srivastava ((2008)[49]) highlighted the significant role of relationship marketing, a substantial segment within holistic marketing, in

delivering and communicating customer value. They emphasized that the primary objective of any business organization is to establish long-term relationships with its customers, ensuring it meets market demands by delivering and communicating consumer value. This, in essence, represents the core goal of relationship marketing. Holistic marketing orientation necessitates reevaluating how to approach the market's new realities in a broader and more comprehensive manner and aspects are significant, highlighting the necessity of a genuine partnership between the organization, suppliers, and distributors. This genuine collaboration is what holistic marketing orientation requires delivering the best possible value to target markets (Lazar, V. (2009) [50]).

Integrated marketing communication encompasses various key initiatives that enable organizations to create, communicate, and deliver value to their customers. It addresses the four key components of marketing activities, often referred to as the marketing mix, which include product, price, place, and promotion. Furthermore, integrated marketing communication plays a crucial role in enhancing various business interactions that are essential for delivering and creating value for customers. These business interactions may take the form of organization-to-organization interactions, collaboration within marketing channels, and internal communication (Rehman,S.U.,&Ibrahim,M.S.(2011)[51]). Holistic marketing not only acknowledges that customers have diverse needs but also caters to these individual customer requirements. This naturally involves a thorough identification of customers' demands and providing what customers need, when and where they need it, at the prices they desire, and in the manner they prefer the company's offerings (Ankita, A. (2012)[52]).

Internal marketing as a crucial tool for effective external marketing, recent developments in the banking industry have emphasized the essential role of employees in achieving superior service quality and customer satisfaction, ultimately leading to customer retention (Ezekiel, P. O. (2014)[53]). Internal marketing emphasize how an organization's initiatives to attract, persuade, nurture, and retain qualified staff capable of delivering greater value to customers typically lead to the transformation of its external relationships. For internal marketing to be effectively implemented, it should be approached as a management process strongly influenced by the organizational culture and leadership climate (Cătălin, M. C.,et al.,. (2014)[54]). social responsibility is the means to create long-term value in banking practices and it enables banks to identify business opportunities and manage risks more effectively (Hernaus, A.I., et al.(2015)[55]).

Banks should develop strategies to understand and meet the needs and expectations of their customers to foster long-term relationships with them, rather than expending significant resources on acquiring new customers. Specifically, commercial banks should learn from their customers and implement activities aimed at establishing, enhancing, and maintaining successful two-way

interactions (Magasi, C.(2016)[56]). Bank managers and owners need to initiate activities and initiatives to strengthen employees' commitment to the organization by fostering a conducive environment before implementing a strategy for its improvement. Bank managers should also ensure that employees provide feedback regarding the benefits, incentives, training, and rewards they receive. This would contribute to enhancing employee engagement and overall performance in the banking sector (Ismail, W., et al. (2017)[57]).

Customer Loyalty

Establishing a strong and enduring connection with customers is a goal for banks, and it often serves as the cornerstone of long-term marketing success. To create such lasting bonds, banks should take into consideration specific strategies. Kotler and Keller (2012) outline four key types of marketing activities that companies use to enhance customer loyalty and retention, which include: Interacting with customers, developing loyalty programs, personalizing marketing efforts and creating institutional ties. Consumer loyalty as a deeply ingrained commitment to consistently repurchase or patronize a preferred product or service in the future. This commitment results in repeated purchasing of the same brand or brand-set, even when situational factors and marketing efforts have the potential to induce switching behavior (Oliver,R.L.(1999)[58]).

Customer loyalty encompasses the behavior of repeat customers, as well as those who provide favorable ratings, reviews, or testimonials. Understanding consumer behavior, the purchasing patterns of customers, and the factors contributing to a satisfying consumer experience is crucial. This experience involves the cognitions and emotions that a consumer undergoes while using a product or service (Belás J., et al.(2016)[59]). The objective for managers should be to transform merely satisfied customers into completely satisfied customers. Loyalty should be attributed only to those customers who are completely satisfied (Brunner,T.A.,et al.(2008)[60]). To manage customer satisfaction effectively and cultivate lasting relationships with customers, firms can employ the following strategies: understanding what can go wrong , focusing on controllable issues, Managing customer expectations, Offering satisfaction guarantees, facilitating the customer complaint process, Implementing relationship programs and Making customer satisfaction measurement an ongoing priority (Chen, et al.(2009)[61]).

Retail Banking

Retail banking involves banks conducting transactions directly with individual consumers, in contrast to transactions with corporations or other banks. The range of services provided includes savings and transactional accounts, mortgages, personal loans, debit cards, and credit cards. Retail banking is regarded as one of the most innovative financial services offered by various

commercial banks, whether they are public sector banks (PSBs), private sector banks, or foreign banks (Rao,R.S.(2014)[62]). Retail banking holds significant potential due to the increasing demand for its products, such as term deposits, consumer durable loans, auto loans, debit and credit cards, ATM facilities, insurance, and online banking. The growth of the retail lending sector has made a substantial contribution to the country's economic development. India, like many other developed nations, has established a well-developed retail banking sector, accounting for a substantial portion of all bank credit. ICICI Bank as one of the early banks in the private sector to recognize the growth potential in retail banking. They have developed comprehensive retail banking models and successfully implemented them through aggressive marketing strategies. This proactive approach has yielded positive results for the bank (Sethuraman, J. (2014)[63]). The biggest problems facing retail banks today is their inability to stand out in an increasingly commoditized and competitive marketplace. Few banks are forging innovation in developing new products. Nor are they connecting with customers in a personalized way as the role of the branch continue to diminish. And new delivery channels, while offering convenience, have created an inconsistent and disjointed experience for many customers (Omarini A. (2019) [64]).

CHAPTER III

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to evaluate the impact of holistic marketing aspects on customer loyalty within Kerala's public sector banks. It delves into the results of the study and outlines the various analytical methods employed by the investigator. The gathered responses from participants was collected, coded and tabulated using SPSS 25.0. The data was dissected using both fundamental and sophisticated statistical techniques. These techniques encompass Mean, Standard Deviation, Reliability analysis, ANOVA, Correlation analysis, Multiple Regression analysis, the test for Multicollinearity, and SEM analysis. The outcomes are divided into two parts. The first, Section A, delves into the general demographics of the participants, while Section B focuses on the impact of holistic marketing elements on customer loyalty in Kerala's public sector banks.

SECTION A

GENERAL PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

The demographic profile of 150 Public Sector Bank customers with regard to their Bank, gender, age, education, marital status, occupation, monthly income, status of usage and type of accounts are presented in Table 3.1

Table 3.1: General Profile of Respondents

Status	Classification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Name of the Bank	State Bank of India	62	41.33
	Canara Bank	35	23.34
	Union Bank of India	21	14
	Bank of Baroda	12	8
	Punjab National Bank	11	7.33
	Indian Overseas Bank	9	6
Total		150	100.00
Gender	Male	88	58.66
	Female	62	41.34
Total		150	100.00

Age	Below 30	53	35.33
	31- 40	60	40
	41- 50	27	18
	Above 50	10	6.67
Total		150	100.00
Education	Higher Secondary or below	14	9.33
	Graduate	38	25.33
	Post- Graduate or above	40	26.67
	Professional Degrees	33	22
	Others	25	16.67
Total		150	100.00
Marital Status	Married	81	54
	Unmarried	51	34
	widowed	14	9.33
	Divorced	4	2.67
Total		150	100.00

Occupation	Govt. Employee	31	20.67
	Private Employee	36	24
	Business	29	19.33
	Professional	22	14.67
	Student	10	6.67
	House Wife	15	10
	Others	7	4.66
Total		150	100.00
Monthly Income	Up to 15,000	30	20
	15,001- 30,000	53	35.33
	30,001-45,000	39	26
	45,001 and above	28	18.67
Total		150	100.00
Status of usage	Less than 1 year	19	12.67
	1 – 5 years	72	48
	5 – 10 years	51	34
	10 – 15 years	5	3.33
	Above 15 years	3	2
Total		150	100.00
Type of Accounts	Saving Account	52	34.68
	Current Account	41	27.33
	Recurring Deposit Account	14	9.33
	Fixed Deposit Account	32	21.33
	Others	11	7.33
Total		150	100.00

Source: Survey Data

From the Table 3.1, we can discern that 41.33% of the participants bank with the State Bank of India, followed by 23.34% with Canara Bank, and 14% with Union Bank of India. Customers of Bank of Baroda account for 8%, while those from Punjab National Bank represent 7.33%, and Indian Overseas Bank customers make up 6%. Furthermore, the table indicates that out of all the respondents, 58.66% are male and 41.34% are female.

The table above provides a breakdown of customer demographics. It's evident that 35.33% of the total customers fall into the age group below 30 years, with 40% in the 31-40 years age bracket.

An 18% portion falls into the 41-50 years age category, while only 6.67% belong to the age group above 50 years. In terms of education, the distribution is as follows: 26.67% of respondents have postgraduate or higher qualifications, 25.33% are graduates, 22% possess professional degrees, 9.21% have educational backgrounds of higher secondary or below, and 16.67% have other qualifications. Regarding marital status, the majority, at 54%, are married. Unmarried individuals constitute 34% of the respondents, while 9.33% are widowed, and the remaining 2.67% are divorced. Occupation-wise, private employees make up the largest group at 24%, followed by government employees at 20.67%. Business people account for 19.33% of the respondents, professionals make up 14.67%, and students represent nearly 6.67%. There are also 10% of respondents who are housewives, and 4.66% fall into the 'others' category. In terms of monthly income, the distribution is as follows: 35.33% of respondents have incomes between 15,001- 30,000, 26% fall into the 30,001-45,000 category, 20% have incomes up to 15,000, and 18.67% fall into the 45,001 and above category.

Regarding the status of usage classification, 48 respondents are between 1 – 5 years category, 34 percent of the respondents are between 5 – 10 years category, 12.67 percent respondents are less than 1 year category, 3.33 percent of respondents are 10 – 15 years category and 2 percent of respondents are above 15 years category. It can be observed that out of 150 respondents, 34.68 per cent of the respondents have Saving Account, 27.33 per cent of the respondents have Current Account, 21.33 per cent of the respondents have Fixed Deposit Account, 9.33 per cent of the respondents have Recurring Deposit Account, whereas 7.33 per cent of the respondents having other Account. This implies that a majority of bank customers are in the age group of 31- 40 years and lower. Mostly Bank customers are married and are private employees, followed by Govt. employees and business persons. It is highlighted that most of the customers have 1- 5 years experience with the banks. Further most Bank customers have a monthly income of more than 15000 rupees.

In terms of usage classification, the data reveals that 48 respondents fall into the 1-5 years category, while 34% of the respondents have a usage history of 5-10 years. Additionally, 12.67% of respondents have used the banking services for less than 1 year, 3.33% for 10-15 years, and 2% for over 15 years. Examining the type of accounts held by the 150 respondents, it is evident that 34.68% of them have a Savings Account, 27.33% have a Current Account, 21.33% have a Fixed Deposit Account, 9.33% maintain a Recurring Deposit Account, and 7.33% hold other types of accounts. This data underscores that the majority of bank customers in this study are in the 31-40 years age group. They are predominantly married and engaged in private employment, followed by government employees and businesspersons. Moreover, it's noteworthy that most of these customers have 1-5 years of experience with their respective banks and typically enjoy a monthly income exceeding 15,000 rupees.

SECTION B

HOLISTIC MARKETING PRACTICES TOWARDS CUSTOMER LOYALTY

This information highlights the practices of selected Public Sector Banks concerning holistic marketing and its impact on customer loyalty. The analysis primarily focuses on four main dimensions of holistic marketing in relation to customer loyalty. Various analytical tools, including Mean, Standard Deviation, Reliability Analysis, Correlation analysis, Multiple Regression analysis, Multicollinearity test, and SEM analysis, were employed to determine the influence of each holistic marketing dimension on customer loyalty.

Reliability Test

The value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient typically falls between 0 and 1, though there's no defined lower boundary for this metric. A value approaching 1.0 indicates higher internal consistency among items in a scale. Based on Table 3.2, with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.774, it can be inferred that the questionnaire possesses a reasonably good level of reliability.

Table –3. 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.774	.774	25

Validity analysis

To assess the data's validity, (Aithal, A., et al. (2020) [65]) the KMO measure and Bartlett's test of Sphericity were conducted. The KMO test returned a value of 0.787, which indicates that the data is appropriate for further analysis, given that the KMO statistic exceeds the threshold of 0.7.

To assess the internal coherence of the statements related to holistic marketing practices and their influence on customer loyalty, the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability test was conducted.

Table 3.3

Reliability Statistics: Holistic Marketing Dimensions on Customer Loyalty

Serial No.	Variables	Number of items	Alpha Value
Holistic Marketing Dimensions on Customer Loyalty			
1	Relationship Marketing	5	.825

2	Integrated Marketing	5	.746
3	Internal Marketing	5	.747
4	Performance Marketing	5	.795
		20	

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.3 reveals that every construct associated with holistic marketing approaches in relation to customer loyalty possesses an alpha value exceeding 0.7. This indicates a high reliability of all the statements presented.

3.3.1 Descriptive Statics of Holistic Marketing Dimensions on Customer Loyalty

To determine the varying importance of different holistic marketing dimensions within Public Sector Banks, as perceived by customers' loyalty, mean scores and standard deviations were computed and are presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3.4: Descriptive Statics of Holistic Marketing Dimensions on Customer Loyalty

Components	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Relationship Marketing	3.4600	1.12106	150
Internal Marketing	3.4867	1.13360	150
Integrated Marketing	3.4800	1.14529	150
Performance Marketing	3.6000	1.11126	150

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.4 provides a detailed statistical overview of the various facets of holistic marketing strategies employed by Public Sector Banks. A visual depiction highlighting the comparative importance of these holistic marketing dimensions, as perceived by customer loyalty, is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1

Relative importance of different Holistic Marketing Dimensions on Customer Loyalty

Figure 3.1 provides a clear insight into the relative importance of different holistic marketing dimensions within Public Sector Banks as perceived by customer loyalty. Performance marketing emerges as the most significant dimension with a mean score of 3.6, followed by internal marketing (mean: 3.4867), and integrated marketing (mean: 3.48). In contrast, relationship marketing (mean: 3.46) is found to be the least critical dimension within the holistic marketing strategies of Public Sector Banks. This highlights that performance marketing stands out as the most influential factor in driving customer loyalty.

3.3.2 Internal Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

In order to ascertain the relationship between internal marketing practices and bank customer loyalty, a null hypothesis was established and evaluated using correlation analysis.

H0: The extent of customer loyalty is significantly determined by the effectiveness of internal marketing strategies.

Table 3.5: Correlation between Internal Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

		Customer Loyalty	Internal Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.673**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000

	N	150	150
Internal Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.5 displays the correlation between the internal marketing practices of Public Sector Banks and customer loyalty. Analyzing the results, we find a correlation coefficient of 0.673 between internal marketing and customer loyalty, with a p-value of .000. This suggests a moderately strong positive correlation between customer loyalty and internal marketing, significant at the 0.01 level.

3.3.3 Integrated Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between integrated marketing practices and the loyalty of customers.

H0: The level of loyalty among customers is markedly influenced by the application of integrated marketing techniques.

Table 3.6: Correlation between Integrated Marketing and Customer Loyalty

		Customer Loyalty	Integrated Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.740**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Integrated Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.740**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.6 reveals that the correlation coefficient between integrated marketing practices and customer loyalty is .740, with a p-value of .000. This indicates a significantly positive and moderately strong correlation between integrated marketing and customer loyalty at the 0.01

significance level.

3.3.4 Performance Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

In order to assess the relationship between performance marketing practices and bank customer loyalty, a null hypothesis was formulated and subsequently tested using correlation analysis.

H0: There exists a significant correlation between the outcomes of performance marketing initiatives and the degree of customer loyalty.

Table 3.7: Correlation between Performance Marketing and Customer Loyalty

		Customer Loyalty	Performance Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.745**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Performance Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.745**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.7 showcases the correlation between performance marketing practices of Public Sector Banks and customer loyalty. Analyzing the results, a correlation coefficient of 0.745 is observed between performance marketing practices and customer loyalty, with a p-value of .000. This suggests a strong and significant positive relationship between performance marketing and customer loyalty at the 0.01 level of significance.

3.3.5 Relationship Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was utilized to evaluate the relationship between relationship marketing practices and the loyalty of customers.

H0: The depth of customer loyalty is substantially affected by the methodologies employed in relationship marketing.

Table 3.8

Correlation between Relationship Marketing and Customer Loyalty

		Customer Loyalty	Relationship Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.654**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Relationship Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.654**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.8 illustrates a correlation coefficient of .654 between relationship marketing practices and customer loyalty, with a p-value of .000. This indicates a moderate yet significantly positive correlation between relationship marketing practices and customer loyalty, significant at the 0.01 level.

3.3.6 Multiple Regression Analysis: Holistic Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

Multiple regression analysis is employed to assess the significant impact of holistic marketing practices of Public Sector Banks on customer loyalty.

H0: The overarching practices of holistic marketing play a pivotal role in shaping the magnitude of customer loyalty.

Table 3.9

Model Summary: Holistic Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.780 ^a	.608	.597	.67950

a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Marketing , Relationship Marketing , Integrated Marketing , Internal Marketing

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.9 indicates that the R Square value is .608, suggesting that 60.8% of the variance in customer loyalty towards holistic marketing is accounted for by the four independent variables: Performance Marketing, Internal Marketing, Relationship Marketing, and Integrated Marketing. This means that these four variables explain 60.8% of the changes in customer loyalty towards holistic marketing practices within Public Sector Banks. Additionally, the adjusted R² offers a refined estimate, indicating that 59.7% of the variability in customer loyalty can be attributed to these four variables. The significance of the R² value for customer loyalty and holistic marketing

practices is further confirmed by the p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$) of the F statistic, as detailed in ANOVA table 3.10.

Table 3.10
ANOVA: Holistic Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	103.885	4	25.971	56.249	.000 ^a
	Residual	66.949	145	.462		
	Total	170.833	149			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Marketing , Relationship Marketing , Integrated Marketing , Internal Marketing

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.11
Coefficients: Holistic Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.824	.196		4.205	.000		
	Relationship Marketing	.199	.099	.208	2.008	.047	.251	3.977
	Internal Marketing	-.301	.141	-.318	-2.126	.035	.121	8.294
	Integrated Marketing	.451	.121	.482	3.721	.000	.161	6.218
	Performance Marketing	.426	.105	.442	4.040	.000	.226	4.431

Dependent Variable:

Customer Loyalty

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.11 presents the correlation coefficients of the independent variables in relation to

customer loyalty. It is evident from the table that the internal marketing variable has a negative correlation with customer loyalty, as indicated by its unstandardized coefficient of -0.301. This suggests that the internal marketing practices of Public Sector Banks may adversely affect customer loyalty within the context of holistic marketing.

Conversely, the other variables, namely performance marketing (0.426), integrated marketing (0.451), and relationship marketing (0.199) are all positively associated with customer loyalty. All these variables have a statistically significant impact on customer loyalty, given that their p-values are below 0.05.

Regarding multicollinearity, the analysis demonstrates its absence, as all the predictor variables in the model - internal marketing, integrated marketing, performance marketing, and relationship marketing - exhibit tolerance levels of 0.121, 0.161, 0.226, and 0.251, respectively. Furthermore, with the VIF values ranging between 1 and 10, there are no signs of multicollinearity, confirming that all the holistic marketing variables are statistically independent of each other.

3.3.7 SEM Analysis: Holistic Marketing Practices and Customer Loyalty

Structural Equation Modeling was utilized to demonstrate how AMOS estimates parameters in Multiple Equation Analysis. It empowered to test the relationship between holistic marketing practices and customer loyalty. It demonstrated the connection between holistic marketing variables (independent variables) and customer loyalty (dependent variable).

Figure 3.2: Standardized Regression Weights of Holistic Marketing Dimensions and

Customer Loyalty.

Figure 3.2 graphically depicts the standardized regression weights for the relationship between holistic marketing dimensions and customer loyalty. The illustration conveys that the combined holistic marketing dimensions account for 61% of the variation in customer loyalty related to banking practices. The data also emphasizes that Integrated Marketing (.48), Relationship Marketing (.21), and Performance Marketing (.44) positively influence customer loyalty. However, Internal Marketing, with a weight of -.32, has a negative bearing on customer loyalty.

CHAPTER IV

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

4.1 FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

This study delves into the relationship between holistic marketing and customer loyalty. It firmly underscores the profound influence of holistic marketing on fostering customer allegiance. The findings validate that, especially in the cutthroat landscape of today's market, holistic marketing emerges as a pivotal strategy for triumph in retail banking. Given that customer loyalty is instrumental in capturing market dominance and carving out a sustainable competitive edge, it's imperative for institutions, especially those like retail banks with frequent customer touchpoints, to deeply understand the dynamics driving customer loyalty. For retail banks, it's essential that frontline staff empathize with customers, offering services that resonate with their needs and expectations. This customer-centric approach can be instrumental in ensuring satisfaction. Moreover, it's crucial for everyone in the banking ecosystem, especially those at senior management levels, to embody holistic marketing principles. The study accentuates the role of internal marketing, emphasizing its significance in enhancing customer loyalty. When bank officials conscientiously uphold banking practices that respect ethical, environmental, legal, and societal contexts, it resonates positively with customers and society at large. For public relations efforts to be effective and mutually beneficial, there needs to be a genuine commitment to the customers' interests. Furthermore, the research corroborates the importance of social responsibility as a determinant of customer loyalty. Banks must recognize the power of their social obligations in retaining dedicated customers. The findings also highlight a significant association between integrated marketing dimensions and customer loyalty. Effective marketing in banking might entail a judicious mix of television, radio, print advertising, PR activities, events, and online presence, all harmoniously working together to convey a consistent brand message. Additionally, the study reveals pertinent insights regarding the role of relationship marketing in retail banking. Tailoring services and messages based on an individual customer's past interactions, demographics, psychographics, and preferences can pave the way for enhanced loyalty. In essence, understanding and acting upon these intricacies can significantly elevate a bank's customer loyalty.

The results confirm that holistic marketing plays a crucial role in influencing customer loyalty within various public sector banks. Comprehensive insights and interpretations from the Correlation Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis can be referenced in Table 4.1.

Table 4:1
Testing of Hypotheses

S. No.	Hypotheses	Test	Result
1	H1: The extent of customer loyalty is significantly determined by the effectiveness of internal marketing strategies.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
2	H2: The level of loyalty among customers is markedly influenced by the application of integrated marketing techniques.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
3	H3: There exists a significant correlation between the outcomes of performance marketing initiatives and the degree of customer loyalty.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
4	H4: The depth of customer loyalty is substantially affected by the methodologies employed in relationship marketing.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
5	H5: The overarching practices of holistic marketing play a pivotal role in shaping the magnitude of customer loyalty.	Multiple Regression Analysis	H0 Accepted

Figure 4.1: Final Accepted Conceptual Model

Based on Multiple Equation Analysis, the impact of holistic marketing on customer loyalty was tested by examining the relationship between several independent variables, performance marketing, relationship marketing, integrated marketing and internal marketing and a dependent variable, namely customer loyalty. Standardized regression weights were employed in this analysis to depict the interrelationships among these variables.

The graphical representation (Fig. 3.3) of these weights showed that the four holistic marketing variables explained 60.8% of the variation in customer loyalty.

4.2 ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL DEVELOPED:

Analyzing research results is a vital step that encompasses evaluating the collected data or established theoretical models. Analyzing the conceptual model crafted for this research is essential to discern its potential relevance to analogous issues. Various analytical frameworks exist in academic research, one of which is the SWOC analysis used for internal analysis (Aithal, A., et al. (2015) [66]) & (Frederick, D. P., et al. (2021) [67]), PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis (Ho, J. K. K. (2014) [68]) & (Song, J., et al. (2017) [69]), and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis (Aithal, A., et al. (2015) [70]) & (Aithal, P. S. (2016) [71]). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the developed model are listed here

as per ABCD analysis framework ((Aithal, P. S. (2017) [72], (Aithal, P. S. et al. (2016) [73]) & (Aithal, P. S. et al. (2016) [74])).

4.2.1 ABCD Listing from Banking Customers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) **Personalized Services:** According to a client's viewpoint, banks that emphasizes on holistic marketing frequently tailor their administrations to individual requirements. This implies that items and administrations are planned keeping the client's particular monetary objectives, difficulties, and propensities at the top of the priority list. This degree of personalization improves the client's banking experience, making it more applicable and productive for them.
- (2) **Consistent and Integrated Experience:** Holistic marketing guarantees a consistent and coordinated client venture, independent of the channel. Whether cooperating with a bank through its site, versatile application, client support hotline, or actual branch, the informing and administration quality are steady. This consistency can altogether upgrade trust and solace levels, prompting more prominent customer loyalty.
- (3) **Proactive Problem-Solving:** Banks that embrace an all encompassing methodology are bound to expect and address possible difficulties before they become issues for the client. By constantly investigating a client's connection with the bank and viewing criticism in a serious way, these organizations can recognize trouble spots and address them proactively. This diminishes disappointment for the client as well as depicts the bank as really thinking often about their prosperity and fulfillment.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) **Enhanced Financial Security:** With a more extensive comprehension of every client's monetary circumstance and objectives, banks can offer more reasonable and secure monetary items. Clients benefit from this by being safeguarded from monetary items that may be dangerous or unsatisfactory for them. They can feel more secure and more safeguarded in their monetary dealings, realizing the bank has their wellbeing on a basic level.
- (2) **Streamlined Services and Efficient Banking:** Holistic marketing frequently means a more coordinated financial framework where administrations are smoothed out. From a client's outlook, this implies quicker reaction times, not so much desk work, but rather more effective exchanges. Whether it's opening another record, looking for a credit, or making ventures, the cycle becomes smoother and easier to understand.
- (3) **Value-added Services and Offers:** As banks accumulate and examine more information about their clients, they can offer some incentive added administrations or exceptional offers custom fitted to individual inclinations and monetary ways of behaving. This

could go from customized monetary counsel to restrictive proposals on Visas or advances. For clients, this implies they can frequently get to more ideal arrangements and administrations that adjust intimately with their necessities and monetary propensities.

(C) Constraints:

- (1) **Privacy Concerns:** As banks assemble and dissect more information to offer an all encompassing financial experience, clients could become careful about how their own and monetary data is being utilized. There's an uplifted feeling of dread toward information breaks, abuse of individual information, or unapproved imparting to outsiders. From the client's perspective, the more information they share, the more weak they could feel.
- (2) **Complexity and Overwhelming Options:** A holistic approach could once in a while prompt a staggering number of choices and administrations, which can befuddle the typical client. The plenty of monetary items, advanced devices, and stages might cause a few clients to have a lost or uncertain outlook on pursuing the best monetary choices.
- (3) **Dependency on Digital Platforms:** With a shift towards a more integrated banking approach, there are areas of strength for on computerized stages. For clients not knowledgeable in innovation, particularly the more established age, this can represent a test. They could feel prohibited or find it challenging to explore the advanced first administrations, yearning for customary,, face-to-face banking interactions.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) **Potential for Over-Personalization:** While customized banking can be gainful, there's a slight line among customization and over-personalization. A few clients might feel that the bank is excessively meddlesome or making presumptions in light of their information, prompting uneasiness or even doubt.
- (2) **Inconsistencies in Service Quality:** Even with a holistic approach, there may be disparities in help quality across different channels. For example, a bank's versatile application could offer a consistent encounter, while its site or actual branch slacks in help. This can baffle clients who anticipate consistency in help quality, regardless of the connection mode.
- (3) **Potential for Miscommunication:** As banks aim to offer a range of services under the umbrella of holistic marketing, there may be cases where advancements, offers, or administrations are not imparted obviously. This can prompt false impressions, where clients feel they were guaranteed one thing yet got another, disintegrating trust in the banking relationship.

4.2.2 ABCD Listing from Banking Service Providers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) **Enhanced Customer Insights:** From a service provider's perspective, a holistic approach to deal with banking considers a more profound comprehension of client conduct, inclinations, and necessities. With the combination of different information sources, banks can determine significant bits of knowledge, empowering them to plan items and administrations that are more lined up with client assumptions. This, thusly, can prompt expanded take-up of administrations, strategically pitching, and upselling valuable open doors.
- (2) **Operational Efficiency:** Executing a thorough technique frequently prompts smoothed out processes. Banks can distinguish redundancies, advance work processes, and influence innovation to mechanize routine assignments. This decreases functional expenses as well as guarantees quicker and more solid help conveyance, upgrading the general client experience.
- (3) **Strengthened Brand Loyalty:** While banking specialist co-ops focus on all encompassing promoting and client driven approaches, it cultivates trust and reliability among clients. A bank that reliably conveys worth and presentations comprehension of its client's requirements is bound to hold those clients over the long haul. This steadfastness decreases client beat, prompting higher lifetime an incentive for every client and guaranteeing a consistent income stream for the bank.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) **Increased Revenue Opportunities:** With a far reaching comprehension of client ways of behaving and needs, banking specialist organizations can successfully designer and market their items. This prompts better item take-up, strategically pitching, and the potential for sending off new, pertinent administrations. Thus, banks can take advantage of numerous income streams and upgrade productivity.
- (2) **Reduced Risk:** By having a more profound, all encompassing perspective on client exchanges and ways of behaving, banks can all the more really screen and foresee expected chances, from credit dangers to extortion location. With better information and experiences, they can carry out measures to proactively moderate these dangers, guaranteeing both the banks and the client's resources are safeguarded.
- (3) **Improved Customer Retention:** Offering a consistent, incorporated banking experience implies clients are bound to remain fulfilled and keep utilizing the bank's

administrations. Holding clients is ordinarily savvier than gaining new ones, prompting supported development and benefit for the bank over the long haul.

(C) Constraints:

- (1) **Integration Challenges:** As banking service providers' aim for a holistic approach, incorporating heritage frameworks with fresher, further developed stages can present critical difficulties. This could include intricacies in information relocation, framework similarity issues, and the requirement for broad preparation for staff, which can all be tedious and costly.
- (2) **Rapid Technological Advancements:** The speed of mechanical change implies that banks need to put resources into refreshing their frameworks and stages constantly. This steady requirement for updates can strain assets, both with regards to funds and human resources. Also, there's the test of guaranteeing that all changes are consistent with industry guidelines.
- (1) **Heightened Customer Expectations:** While a holistic approach improves the client experience, it likewise sets better standards for administration quality. Living up to these raised assumptions reliably can be testing, particularly when outer variables (like monetary slumps or worldwide emergencies) influence administration conveyance. Inability to measure up to these assumptions can prompt client disappointment and steady loss.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) **Increased Costs: Implementing:** a holistic approach frequently requires huge interests in innovation, preparing, and process updates. This can bring about significant forthright expenses, and there's no quick assurance of a relating expansion in income or piece of the pie. Banks could likewise confront repeating costs in refreshing and keeping up with these new frameworks..
- (2) **Complexity in Implementation:** Adopting a holistic strategy might confuse the functional cycle, to some extent at first. Guaranteeing that different divisions and frameworks work consistently can challenge. It could likewise request changes in hierarchical culture, requiring purchase in from all levels of the association, which can be hard to accomplish.

(3) **Vulnerability to System Failures:** As banks become more interconnected and reliant upon incorporated frameworks, they could turn out to be more defenseless against framework wide disappointments or digital assaults. An issue or break in one region might possibly upset or compromise different capabilities, presenting dangers to the two tasks and client trust.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this discussion underscores the significance of holistic marketing as an indispensable strategy for effectively conceptualizing and executing programs and practices to navigate the intricacies of the market. It emphasizes the essential role of employing all four components of holistic marketing to comprehensively address customer loyalty within the retail banking sector. Holistic marketing, beyond merely advertising a bank's products and services, plays a pivotal role in shaping the bank's brand image at the societal level by integrating programs and practices that resonate with the broader community. Furthermore, all four dimensions of holistic marketing are instrumental in delivering and communicating the inherent value to consumers in the banking sector. This study was designed to examine the impact of holistic marketing on customer loyalty, and the results affirm a significant influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. It's essential to recognize that loyalty is intrinsically linked to satisfaction, and this is not an isolated factor. As indicated by the tests and findings, all the predictors - relationship marketing, internal marketing, integrated marketing, and performance marketing - exhibit positive correlations with customer loyalty. Managers must keep in mind that customer expectations are not solely based on what similar service providers are doing but also encompass the benchmark of the best service providers in general. Building customer loyalty is contingent on creating positive differentiation, which is typically achieved through delivering superior customer service.

SUGGESTIONS

It is recommended to the public banking sector to determine struggle in a way that will take out irrelevant misfortune and burden to customers. This will construct the customers' loyalty that will help banks in acquiring the upper hand in a rising contest in the retail banking sector. Retail banking sector need to satisfy exceptionally requesting customers since they will proceed with utilize the bank the services is satisfied. This study prescribes that banks need to place more regard for draw in customers in terms of relationship marketing integrated marketing, and performance marketing. To be solid association among bank and customer is likewise fundamental for bank to maintaining a good business relationship such as organizing festive celebration, potential customer's celebration and others. Bank should pressure in the enrollment arrangements particularly for those are bringing the front picture of bank since they are addressed for the benefit of bank. However, it's worth noting that this research has limitations, as it relies on available data and is limited to the state of Kerala. To enhance the depth of understanding, further research is recommended. Future studies could explore the impact of holistic marketing dimensions on customer loyalty in the context of public sector banks. Additionally, investigations can be conducted to assess the effects of holistic marketing on customer loyalty in private sector banks, foreign banks, and co-operative banks.

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An Analytical Study of Applications of Artificial Intelligence on Banking Practices

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An Analytical Study of Applications of Artificial Intelligence on Banking Practices

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to enhance the creativity, adaptability, and flexibility of enterprises beyond their current capabilities. Many businesses are already leveraging AI to increase productivity and competitiveness, as well as drive digital transformation in various industries. In India, AI is assisting banks in upgrading their operations across the board, from traditional to digital banking practices. This study is based on the application of AI on various virtual assistants provided by public sector banks in Kerala as well as the recent advancements and emergence of virtual banking and modern banking trends.

Design: In this study, both descriptive and analytical research designs were employed. A standardized questionnaire was administered to 150 Bank employees to collect primary data and demographic information. To ensure the validity and reliability of the study, a pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha test were conducted to assess the variables of measures. The collected data were analyzed using correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, and Multicollinearity.

Findings/Results: The current research findings support the notion that artificial intelligence has a significant impact on various practices within public-sector banking. The study's results demonstrate that the independent variables, including Chatbot, Robo Advice, Predictive Analytics, Cyber security, and Credit Scoring, collectively serve as significant predictors (64%) of banking practices.

Paper Type: Descriptive and Analytical Research

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Banking practices, Modern banking system, Virtual banking, Digital transformation.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Digital transformation is viewed as one of the most eminent drivers of organizations that contribute towards the conveyance of significant worth to their clients in a cutthroat, rapidly changing business environment (Kumari, A., et al. (2020) [1]). AI is currently acquiring wide acknowledgment as one of the most fundamental digital transformation-empowering influences among different businesses (Henkel, J., et al. (2020) [2]). Artificial intelligence (AI) helps in working with ventures to be creative, flexible, and versatile in the unique cutthroat business climate (Tekin, E., et al. (2021) [3]). The significant utilization of artificial intelligence is to upgrade the efficiency and intensity of an extensive variety of organizations that are driving toward digital transformation (Alzahrani, M., et al. (2021) [4]). Indian banking industries are exceptionally adjusting towards mechanical progressions by involving mechanical apparatuses and systems to serve new-age clients and grow their financial practices by guaranteeing quality services (Kshetri, N., et al. (2020) [5]). AI is playing a crucial part in overhauling the financial practices and tasks of different Indian banks in all cases, from accounting to sales to contracts and cyber security (Jindal, V., et al. (2020) [6]). In India, public sector banks play a predominant part in expanding different banking services, albeit throughout the long-term rivalry has

significantly expanded because of the rise of the private sector and foreign banks. As of now, there are 12 public sector banks in India. Ongoing turns of events and the emergence of virtual banking, the application of AI in banking practices, and factors contributing towards the successful use of AI in various banking practices with special reference to public sector banks in Kerala are explained in this study. The researcher has taken the topic "AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON BANKING PRACTICES", to know how AI is fortifying the competitiveness of public sector banks in Kerala through its variables such as Chatbot, Robo Advice, Predictive Analytics, Cyber security, and Credit Scoring.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Various researchers and specialists made sense of that Artificial Intelligence as a quick creation of innovation across the world and its applications in the financial business (Lu, X., et al. (2018) [7]). The banking sector is becoming perhaps the earliest adopter of artificial intelligence (Vatansever, V., et al. (2021) [8]). Artificial intelligence (AI) can possibly work with ventures to become more creative, flexible, and versatile than ever (Ghazamfar, M. A., et al. (2021) [9]). Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used to enhance productivity and competitiveness, as well as drive digital transformation in various industries (Wang, M., et al. (2021) [10]). In India, Artificial intelligence is aiding banks in updating their operations in all cases, from accounting to sales to contracts and cyber security (Sahu, S. K., et al. (2020) [11]). Various applications of AI in mining the monetary exchange information by the multiplication of advanced installments and other financial administrations for better checking, anticipating, and breaking down purchaser conduct towards computerized financial administrations (Aggarwal, S., et al. (2020) [12]). Artificial intelligence cannot just supplant human resources in that frame of mind to a limited extent yet additionally upgrade its presentation past human benchmarks (Brynjolfsson, E., et al. (2017) [13]). AI has been viewed as utilized by associations all over the planet for the location of abnormalities (Song, X., et al. (2021) [14]). It is used to establish optimal investment strategies (Liao, L., et al. (2021) [15]). Artificial intelligence comprises commonly two key thoughts. First, it includes concentrating on human cerebrums like how their point of view functions, and besides it helps to address those cycles through machine learning. (Le Cun, Y., et al. (2015) [16]). AI can fundamentally further develop fraud detection and anticipation by dissecting enormous volumes of information and distinguishing patterns of fraudulent behavior (Li, X., et al. (2020) [17]). Similarly, AI can support credit risk investigation by robotizing the course of credit scoring and decreasing the gamble of defaults (Li, S., et al. (2021) [18]). Moreover, AI-based chatbots can upgrade client support by giving customized and productive help to clients (Saha, S., et al. (2018) [19]). Artificial intelligence can work on the productivity of banking activities via computerizing monotonous undertakings and diminishing mistakes (Chen, J., et al. (2019) [20]). AI-based predictive analytics can also help banks to pursue more exact choices and further develop risk management (Wang, J., et al. (2020) [21]).

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM :

The researcher has identified the following research questions based on the problem discussion.

- (1) In what ways does AI aid banks in enhancing their banking practices?
- (2) To what extent do various applications of AI impact banking practices?

4. OBJECTIVES:

- (1) To analyze the impact of AI applications on banking practices in public-sector banks.
- (2) To develop a conceptual model of the factors affecting of AI in the banking sector.
- (3) To prove the conceptual model empirically by testing the hypotheses.
- (4) To compare the associations between AI applications and banking practices, as well as to differentiate the advantages of these associations.
- (5) To evaluate the final conceptual model developed using empirical study.
- (6) To analyze the conceptual model developed using ABCD analysis framework.
- (7) To suggest how to enhance banking practices using AI aids.

5. CONCEPTUAL MODEL :

By leveraging Artificial Intelligence, banks can effectively handle large volumes of data at high speeds to gain valuable insights. Additionally, the integration of digital payment systems, AI-powered chatbots, and biometric fraud detection technologies enables banks to provide high-quality services to a wider

customer base (Damasia, J., (2021) [22]). In his study, he identified the five primary applications of artificial intelligence in banking as chatbots, robo-advisors, predictive analytics, cyber security, and credit scoring. AI-based chatbots can provide personalized and efficient support to customers, such as answering frequently asked questions, providing transaction details, and helping with account management (Liao, Q., et al. (2019) [23]). Chatbots can also help banks save time and costs by automating customer service tasks and reducing the need for human support (Gholami, R., et al. (2019) [24]). AI-powered robo-advisors can assist customers with investment decisions, such as suggesting suitable portfolios based on their risk tolerance and financial goals (Kim, K. J., et al. (2017) [25]). Robo-advisors can provide 24/7 investment advice and portfolio management, and can also help banks reach a wider range of customers who may not have access to traditional financial advisors (Agarwal, S., et al. (2018) [26]). AI-based predictive analytics can help banks make more accurate decisions and improve risk management by analyzing large volumes of data and identifying patterns and trends (Kusiak, A., et al. (2017) [27]). Predictive analytics can be used for fraud detection, credit risk evaluation, and customer behavior analysis, among other applications (Manikandan, M., et al. (2020) [28]).

AI-based cybersecurity solutions can help banks detect and prevent cyber threats, such as phishing attacks and malware, by analyzing network traffic and identifying suspicious activity (Gupta, A., et al. (2019) [29]). AI can also help banks monitor and secure customer data and transactions, and comply with regulatory requirements (Caron, P., et al. (2019) [30]). AI can support credit risk investigation by automating the process of credit scoring and reducing the risk of defaults (Chen, H., et al. (2019) [31]). AI can analyze a range of data sources, such as credit histories, income, and employment status, to provide more accurate and timely credit assessments, which can help banks make informed lending decisions (Bao, Y., et al. (2019) [32]).

Based on the theoretical framework and a review of existing literature, six postulates for the factors affecting of AI in banking sector are developed:

- (1) Postulate 1: Increased Chatbot utilization can lead to the development of more advanced AI technologies and applications in the banking sector, as banks gain experience in implementing and optimizing Chatbot systems.
- (2) Postulate 2: Robo-advisors can provide cost savings for banks, as they can reduce the need for human advisors in certain investment management roles. This can improve the overall profitability of banks.
- (3) Postulate 3: Increased use of predictive analytics in banking practices will lead to greater accuracy and efficiency in financial decision-making. Predictive analytics can help banks to analyze large amounts of data and identify trends and patterns that can inform investment, lending, and risk management decisions.
- (4) Postulate 4: The implementation of cyber security measures can reduce the risk of data breaches and cyber attacks, which can have significant financial and reputational impacts on banks.
- (5) Postulate 5: Credit scoring practices can help banks to stay competitive in the marketplace by offering more personalized and targeted lending products to customers.
- (6) Postulate 6: AI can help banks to make more accurate and informed decisions by analyzing vast amounts of data in real-time, allowing for more effective risk management, investment strategies, and customer engagement.

Using the above six postulates, a conceptual model was constructed to investigate which are the factors affecting of AI in banking sector and how the use of AI applications impacts banking practices in public sector banks in Kerala. In light of this study, research has designed the proposed conceptual model (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Proposed Conceptual Model

To achieve the objectives of the conceptual model, the study proposes several hypotheses based on the factors affecting AI in the banking sector, including chatbots, robo-advisors, predictive analytics, cyber security, and credits scoring used are given below:

6. HYPOTHESES :

- H1: There may have a significant positive correlation between chatbot utilization and banking practices.
- H2: There may have a significant positive association between the use of robo-advisors and banking practices.
- H3: There may have a significant positive link between the use of predictive analytics and banking practices.
- H4: There may have a significant positive correlation between cybersecurity measures and banking practices.
- H5: There may have a significant positive correlation between credit scoring practices and banking practices.
- H6: AI has a positive impact on banking practices.

7. METHODOLOGY TO PROVE THE MODEL :

This study utilized a research design that incorporated both descriptive and analytical research methods. The primary data was collected through a pretested questionnaire method, which was modified based on the results of a pilot study. The data collection period spanned from August 2022 to October 2022, and the sample included 150 banking employees from various public sector banks in Kerala, India. To analyze the data, statistical tools such as correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, and multicollinearity test were employed.

7.1 Reliability Test:

According to the information provided in Table 1, Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.795, which indicates that the reliability of the questionnaire is moderately good.

Table - 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.795	.795	30

7.2 Validity analysis:

To test the validity of the data (Aithal, A., et al. (2020) [33]) the KMO measure and Bartlett's test of Sphericity were conducted. The KMO test resulted in a value of 0.798, indicating that the data is suitable for further analysis, as the KMO statistic is greater than 0.7.

8. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS :**8.1 Correlation analysis:****Table 2: Correlation analysis**

S. No.	Hypotheses	Coefficient of correlation	Interpretation
1	There may have a significant positive correlation between chatbot utilization and banking practices.	0.667	Moderate positive correlation
2	There may have a significant positive association between the use of robo-advisors and banking practices.	0.663	Moderate positive correlation
3	There may have a significant positive link between the use of predictive analytics and banking practices.	0.585	Moderate positive correlation
4	There may have a significant positive correlation between cybersecurity measures and banking practices.	0.676	Moderate positive correlation
5	There may have a significant positive correlation between credit scoring practices and banking practices.	0.643	Moderate positive correlation

The table presented above displays the results of the correlation analysis conducted to examine the relationship between the applications of artificial intelligence and banking practices, in accordance with the hypotheses of the study. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the strength of the relationship between the variables. Based on the correlation analysis, it can be observed that there exist moderate positive relationships between the applications of artificial intelligence and banking practices.

8.2 Multiple Regression Analysis:**Table 3.a: Model Summary: Artificial Intelligence and banking practices**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.798 ^a	.641	.634	2.46438

a. Predictors: (Constant), Chatbot, Robo Advice, Predictive Analytics, Cyber Security, and Credit Scoring. Source: Survey Data

Table 3.a indicates that the R Square value is .641, indicating that 64.1% of the variations in banking practices are accounted for by the five independent variables, namely Chatbot, Robo Advice, Predictive Analytics, Cybersecurity, and Credit Scoring.

Table 3.b: Coefficients: Artificial intelligence and banking practices

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	4.467	1.026		4.217	.000		
Predictive Analytics	-.088	.067	-.101	-1.484	.126	.285	3.276
Chatbot	.277	.089	.232	4.171	.000	.472	2.086
Robo Advice	.335	.061	.277	4.567	.000	.344	2.802
Credit Scoring	-.030	.044	-.007	-.360	.612	.657	1.436
Cyber Security	.546	.054	.480	9.671	.000	.565	1.737

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.b displays the coefficients for various variables and their relationship with banking practices. The unstandardized coefficients for predictive analytics (-.088) and credit scoring (-.030) are negative, which means they have a negative impact on banking practices. On the other hand, Chatbot (.277), Robo Advice (.335), and Cyber Security (.546) have positive unstandardized coefficients, indicating a positive relationship with banking practices. The p-values for Chatbot, Robo Advice, and Cyber Security are 0.000, which means they have a significant influence on banking practices. However, Credit Scoring and Predictive Analytics have high significant values (0.612 and 0.126 respectively), indicating that they have no effect on banking practices. The tolerance values for all the predicted variables are between 0.285 and 0.657, which indicates that multicollinearity has no effect on the results. Furthermore, the VIF values for all the variables are between 1 and 10, which indicates that there is no multicollinearity. Therefore, it can be concluded that all the artificial intelligence variables are statistically independent of each other.

9. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION :

The main focus of this study was to investigate the relationship between AI and banking practices among banking employees working in different public sector banks located in Kerala. The research findings suggest that AI is a significant technique for banking practices, particularly in the current progressively aggressive and dynamic workspace. The results of the study provide support for the notion that AI is a huge element that influences banking practices among employees working in various public sector banks. The hypotheses formulated and tested by using Correlation analysis are shown in table 4.

Table 4: Testing of Hypotheses

S. No.	Hypotheses	Test	Result
1	There may have a significant positive correlation between chatbot utilization and banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
2	There may have a significant positive association between the use of robo-advisors and banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
3	There may have a significant positive link between the use of predictive analytics and banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted

4	There may have a significant positive correlation between cybersecurity measures and banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
5	There may have a significant positive correlation between credit scoring practices and banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
6	AI has a positive impact on banking practices.	Multiple Regression Analysis	H0 Accepted

Fig. 2: Final Accepted Conceptual Model

Based on Multiple Equation Analysis, the impact of AI on banking practices was tested by examining the relationship between several independent variables, namely chatbots, robo-advisors, predictive analytics, cyber security, and credit scoring, and a dependent variable, namely banking practices. The analysis utilized standardized regression weights to illustrate the relationship between the variables. The graphical representation (Fig. 2) of these weights showed that the five AI variables explained 64.1% of the variation in banking practices.

10. ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL DEVELOPED :

Analysis of research results refers to the process of examining and interpreting gathered information or developed conceptual models. It is essential to analyze the developed conceptual model for its use in solving similar types of problems. In this section, we have analyzed the use of this newly developed conceptual model on the impact of AI on banking practices from its stakeholders' point of view. There

are many analysis frameworks used in scholarly research which include SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis (Aithal, A., et al. (2015) [34] & (Frederick, D. P., et al. (2021) [35]), PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis (Ho, J. K. K. (2014) [36] & (Song, J., et al. (2017) [37]), and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis (Aithal, A., et al. (2015) [38] & (Aithal, P. S. (2016) [39]). The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the developed model are listed here as per ABCD analysis framework ((Aithal, P. S. (2017) [40], (Aithal, P. S. et al. (2016) [41] & (Aithal, P. S. et al. (2016) [42]).

10.1 ABCD Listing from Banking Customers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) Personalized customer experience
- (2) Improved security
- (3) Faster and accurate decision making
- (4) Cost reduction

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Fraud detection and prevention
- (2) Improved efficiency
- (3) 24/7 availability
- (4) Faster loan approvals

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Technical complexity
- (2) Job displacement
- (3) Integration and implementation challenges
- (4) Ethical considerations

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) Lack of human interaction
- (2) Privacy and security concerns
- (3) Limited understanding of complex situations

10.2 ABCD Listing from Banking Service Providers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) Automation of routine tasks
- (2) Cost reduction
- (3) Improved fraud detection
- (4) Data-driven insights

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Enhanced risk management
- (2) Personalized customer interactions
- (3) Automation of compliance and regulatory processes
- (4) Improved customer service

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Technical complexity
- (2) Data quality and availability
- (3) Regulatory compliance
- (4) Ethical considerations

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) Customer acceptance
- (2) Limited interpretability
- (3) Reliance on historical data

11. RECOMMENDATIONS & SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH :

While the banking sector has for quite some time been technology-dependent and information-concentrated, new information-empowered AI technology has the ability to drive advancement further and quicker than at any other time. AI can assist with further developing proficiency, empower a development plan, help separation, and oversee risk and administrative requirements, and decidedly impact customer experience. Over 60% of bank customers' accept customized services as one of the key factors for them to have trust in their banks. As per the latest reviews, only 30% of public sector banks offer personalization that addresses clients' issues in a fitting overall setting. Consequently, banks should contribute like never before to customize the administration's proposal to clients and, thus, hold their trust and steadfastness. Banks should utilize data-driven AI abilities to lead miniature divisions of existing clients and possibilities. This degree of granularity can help banks all the more precisely anticipate client and prospect need and ways of behaving. In view of the findings, the recommendation has been advanced to help key and strategy drives in this subject and area worldwide.

12. CONCLUSION :

The developing adoption of AI vows to lastingly affect the banking industry. Banks are coming to perceive the progressions that trend-setting innovations can cultivate, and, all the more significantly, they are embracing them. In the long haul, it is possible that banks' cutthroat highlights could rely upon building technological establishments and cycles to completely understand the advantages that AI vows to convey. In conclusion, these studies exhibit the possible advantages of AI in the public banking sector, including further developed effectiveness, exactness, the risk to the board, and client experience. Notwithstanding, there is a requirement for fitting guidelines and moral contemplations to guarantee the dependable and secure execution of AI in banking practices.

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The Influence of Gamification on Customer Experience in Digital Banking Practices

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *In a world that increasingly revolves around technology and digital interactions, businesses strive to provide engaging and personalized experiences to their customers. In the realm of banking, this endeavor has given rise to the incorporation of gamification techniques to enhance customer engagement and satisfaction. Gamification, the utilization of game plan standards and mechanics in non-game settings, has arisen as a useful asset in various industries, including digital banking. This article explores the influence of gamification on customer experience in the domain of digital banking practices. The researcher has chosen the topic "The Influence of Gamification on Customer Experience in Digital Banking Practices" to examine how gamification strategies, including badges, points, leaderboards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games, are enhancing the competitive edge of private sector banks in Kerala.*

Design: *In this study, a combination of descriptive and analytical research designs was utilized. Primary data and demographic information were gathered through the administration of a standardized questionnaire to a sample of 150 bank customers. To validate the study and ensure its reliability, a preliminary survey was undertaken, and the Cronbach's Alpha test was used to evaluate the metrics of the study. The amassed data underwent analysis through techniques such as correlation, multiple regression, and tests for multicollinearity to understand the intrinsic relationships and determinants in the research.*

Findings/Results: *This research offers concrete empirical proof highlighting the profound impact of gamification on the customer experience in digital banking, particularly within the private sector. The study's outcomes reveal that the chosen independent factors, namely badges, points, leaderboards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games, collectively play a significant role (accounting for 54% of the variance) in predicting customer experience.*

Paper Type: *Descriptive and Analytical Research*

Keywords: Gamification, Digital banking practices, Technology and digital interactions, Customer experience, Gamification strategies

1. INTRODUCTION :

In recent years, the digital banking landscape has witnessed a significant transformation as financial institutions seek innovative ways to enhance customer experience and engagement (Feyen, E., et al. (2021) [1]). One strategy that has gained considerable attention is the integration of gamification elements into digital banking practices (Chauhan, S., et al. (2021) [2]). Gamification entails the integration of game-design concepts and techniques into non-gaming environments with the objective of enhancing user participation and enthusiasm. (Mauroner, O. (2019) [3]). By incorporating elements such as points, badges, leaderboards, challenges, and rewards, gamification strives to make banking activities more enjoyable, interactive, and immersive for customers (Nasirzadeh, E., et al. (2020) [4]). In recent years, India's banking sector has experienced a significant transformation, primarily fueled by

the incorporation of digital innovations (Belgavi, V., (2021) [5]). As traditional brick-and-mortar banks shift their focus toward providing seamless and user-friendly digital banking experiences, customer engagement and satisfaction have become paramount (Bauer, H. H., et al. (2005) [6]). This article aims to explore the influence of gamification on customer experience in digital banking practices, analyzing its impact on engagement, loyalty, and overall satisfaction. The researcher has taken the topic "The Influence of Gamification on Customer Experience in Digital Banking Practices", to know how Gamification is fortifying the competitiveness of private sector banks in Kerala through its variables such as Badges, Points, Leader boards, Rewards, Progress Bars, Trivia, Opinion polls and Mini- Games (Lakshya A. (2022) [7]).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Researchers and experts have recognized gamification as a rapidly emerging technological advancement worldwide, with wide-ranging applications in the field of banking practices. (Rodrigues, L. F., et al. (2016) [8]). The integration of gamification elements in digital banking aims to transform routine financial transactions into enjoyable and interactive experiences (Malarout, N., et al. (2020) [9]). The different gamification elements and their potential to improve customer experience, loyalty, and engagement in digital banking practices (Huseynov, F. (2020) [10]). Banks, by adopting gamification strategies, aim to offer their customers a more personalized and enriched experience, leading to heightened customer loyalty and retention (Nasirzadeh, E., & Fathian, M. (2020) [11]). The combination of gamification components is viewed as a way to improve client collaborations, give constant input, and prize clients for accomplishing explicit achievements (Lu, H.-P., et al. (2020) [12]). Gamified highlights can be utilized to teach clients about different monetary items and administrations. By introducing complex monetary ideas in an intelligent and agreeable way, banks can work on monetary education among their client base (Bayuk, J., et al. (2019) [13]). The progress of gamification lies in its capacity to take advantage of the natural human craving for rivalry, accomplishment, and prizes, making banking exercises more charming and spurring for clients (Sheetal, et al. (2022) [14]). As banks adopt gamification, they must also consider the ethical implications, such as safeguarding customer data and ensuring that gamified features do not inadvertently encourage risky financial behaviors (Hass, D., et al. (2022) [15]).

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM :

From the problem identified, the researcher has posited the subsequent research questions:

- (1) In what ways does gamification assist banks in improving the experience of their customers?
- (2) What is the level of influence exerted by different gamification elements on the customer experience?

4. OBJECTIVES :

- (1) To scrutinize the impact of gamification on the customer experience within private-sector digital banking platforms.
- (2) To develop a conceptual framework that pinpoints the determinants that shape the influence of gamification on the customer experience in digital banking operations.
- (3) To empirically validate the conceptual model by conducting hypothesis testing.
- (4) To compare the relationships between gamification and customer experience, as well as highlight the unique benefits of these relationships.
- (5) To empirically assess the constructed conceptual model.
- (6) To dissect the formulated conceptual model utilizing the ABCD analytical framework.
- (7) To recommend approaches for bolstering digital banking methods by integrating gamification techniques.

5. CONCEPTUAL MODEL :

Gamification has emerged as a potent strategy to amplify customer experience in the realm of digital banking, yet it shouldn't be perceived as a panacea (Ghazi Kalshroodi, M. A., et al. (2023) [16]). For fruitful deployment, banks need to intricately understand their clientele, the essence of their offerings, and the objectives they aim to realize through gamification. A nuanced comprehension of user habits, inclinations, and challenges is paramount (Nuijten, R. C. Y. (2022) [17]). Those gamification approaches that resonate with the distinct needs and aspirations of the bank's clientele, instilling a sense

of bespoke interaction and autonomy in their financial endeavors, will stand out (Bitrian, P., et al. (2021) [18]). By assimilating elements such as badges, points, leaderboards, and rewards, among others, gamification is bolstering banks' competitive edge (Likitha, A. (2022) [19]). Each constituent plays an integral role in magnifying customer involvement, gratification, and allegiance, adding layers to the bank's competitive positioning (Sachdeva, H. (2023) [20]). For instance, badges serve as graphical commemorations of milestones or accomplishments, earned by customers for completing designated tasks or achieving set benchmarks (Kanazawa, M. (2023) [21]). They give a feeling of achievement and acknowledgment to clients, inspiring them to investigate different financial highlights and complete more exchanges (Korsun, J. (2023) [22]). Badges advance a sensation of movement and achievement, upgrading consumer loyalty and empowering proceeded with commitment with the bank's administrations (Grochowska, I. (2023) [23]). Points go about as a type of virtual money that clients can collect through different connections with the bank's computerized stage (Roncone, V., et al. (2022) [24]). They make a gamified economy where clients are boosted to play out specific activities, like making exchanges, alluding companions, or utilizing explicit administrations, to procure more points (Walker, H. (2022) [25]). Points add a serious and compensating aspect toward the financial experience, empowering clients to partake effectively and take a stab at higher prizes (LaFleur, G. (2022) [26]). Leader boards display show the accomplishments and rankings of clients in light of their places or other execution measurements. They make sound rivalry among clients, driving commitment as clients look to climb the positions and beat others. Leader boards cultivate a feeling of local area and social cooperation, rousing clients to turn out to be all the more effectively engaged with the bank's computerized biological system (Laming, T. (2020) [27]). Rewards are substantial impetuses proposed to clients for finishing explicit jobs or accomplishing predefined objectives. These prizes can incorporate limits, cash back, or select offers. By giving significant prizes, banks build up sure ways of behaving, energize client dedication, and increment the apparent benefit of drawing in with their advanced financial administrations (Chen, J. (2022) [28]). Progress bars visually represent the advancement of customers toward their goals or objectives. They provide a sense of direction and accomplishment, helping customers understand how close they are to completing specific tasks. Progress bars create a feeling of momentum, encouraging users to stay committed to their financial objectives and complete the desired actions (Comarch. (2023) [29]). Trivia and opinion polls add an interactive and educational element to the banking experience. They allow customers to participate in quizzes or express their opinions on various financial topics. By incorporating these elements, banks can engage customers in fun and informative activities, fostering a deeper understanding of financial products and services (Dudovicz, P. (2023) [30]). Mini-games are interactive activities designed to entertain and engage customers while subtly promoting financial literacy and responsible banking behavior. These games offer a break from traditional banking tasks and create a more enjoyable and memorable experience. By incorporating mini-games, banks can build stronger emotional connections with their customers, increasing brand loyalty and advocacy (Korsun, J. (2023) [31]).

Drawing from the theoretical foundation and a comprehensive exploration of prevailing literature, this study posits eight postulates. These are aimed at delineating the determinants that shape the nexus between gamification and the customer experience within digital banking paradigms:

- (1) Postulate 1: The presence of badges in digital banking practices positively impacts customer experience by providing a sense of accomplishment and recognition for completing tasks or reaching goals.
- (2) Postulate 2: Points as progress indicators in digital banking practices enhance customer experience by incentivizing and motivating users to perform tasks or actions.
- (3) Postulate 3: Leader boards in digital banking practices create a sense of competition among users, leading to increased engagement and improved customer experience.
- (4) Postulate 4: Offering rewards and deals in digital banking practices excite users, boosts user retention, and fosters loyalty, thereby enhancing customer experience.
- (5) Postulate 5: Progress bars in digital banking practices motivate users to complete tasks by visually tracking their progress, resulting in improved customer experience.
- (6) Postulate 6: Trivia-based engagements in digital banking platforms serve to bolster user proficiency by heightening awareness around pivotal themes and offering pertinent data, thereby amplifying the overall customer experience.

(7) Postulate 7: Opinion polls in digital banking practices allow users to provide feedback, making them feel valued and improving their overall experience.

(8) Postulate 8: Incorporating mini-games with valuable rewards and deals in digital banking practices adds a fun element to the user experience, increasing engagement and improving customer satisfaction.

Given the aforementioned postulates, a conceptual model was conceived to scrutinize the determinants of the study. The model incorporates the key elements of gamification and their relationship with customer experience. In light of this study, research has developed a proposed conceptual model (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Proposed Conceptual Model

To address the goals set out by the conceptual model, this research formulates various hypotheses rooted in the elements. These elements encompass badges, points, leaderboards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games. The subsequent sections will delineate these hypotheses in detail.

6. HYPOTHESES :

H1: The presence of badges is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.

H2: The utilization of points is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.

H3: The inclusion of leaderboards is significantly positively connected to customer experience in digital banking practices.

H4: Offering rewards is significantly positively correlated with customer experience in digital banking practices.

H5: The presence of progress bars is significantly positively related to customer experience in digital banking practices.

H6: Incorporating trivia activities is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.

H7: The implementation of opinion polls is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.

H8: The inclusion of mini-games is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.

H9: The application of gamification positively impacts on customer experience in digital banking practices.

7. METHODOLOGY TO PROVE THE MODEL :

The research approach employed in this research integrated both descriptive and analytical techniques. Primary data was gathered through the administration of a pretested questionnaire, refined based on insights from a preliminary pilot study. The period of data collection extended from March 2023 through June 2023, with a sample size comprising 150 banking customers drawn from diverse private sector banks within Kerala, India. The data was subjected to a comprehensive analysis using statistical techniques including correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, and multicollinearity tests.

Reliability Test:

As reflected in Table 1, the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.805, implying a moderate to strong reliability of the questionnaire utilized in the research.

Table - 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.805	.805	30

Validity analysis:

To validate the data, the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) measure and Bartlett's test of Sphericity were executed (Aithal, A., et al. (2020) [32]). The resulting KMO value was 0.808, denoting that the data is apt for subsequent analyses.

8. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS :

8.1 Correlation analysis:

Table 2: Correlation analysis

S. No.	Hypotheses	Coefficient of correlation	Interpretation
1	H1: The presence of badges is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.696	Moderate positive correlation
2	H2: The utilization of points is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.701	Moderate positive correlation
3	H3: The inclusion of leaderboards is significantly positively connected to customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.675	Moderate positive correlation
4	H4: Offering rewards is significantly positively correlated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.706	Moderate positive correlation
5	H5: The presence of progress bars is significantly positively related to customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.672	Moderate positive correlation

6	H6: Incorporating trivia activities is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.659	Moderate positive correlation
7	H7: The implementation of opinion polls is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.709	Moderate positive correlation
8	H8: The inclusion of mini-games is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	0.687	Moderate positive correlation

The table depicted above exhibits the outcomes of the correlation analysis performed to explore the associations between the variables, in line with the study's hypotheses. The Pearson correlation coefficient was employed to gauge the magnitude of the associations between the variables. The results of the correlation analysis suggest that moderate positive relationships exist among the factors.

8.2 Multiple Regression Analysis:

Table 3.a: Model Summary: Gamification and Customer Experience

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.698 ^a	.541	.534	1.76338

a. Predictors: (Constant), badges, points, leader boards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games. Source: Survey Data

Table 3.a indicates that the R Square value is .541, indicating that 54.1% of the variations in customer experience are accounted for by the eight independent variables, namely badges, points, leader boards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games.

Table 3.b: Coefficients: Gamification and Customer Experience

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	4.067	1.002		3.807	.000		
Badges	-.078	.057	-.101	-1.044	.116	.275	3.251
Points	.219	.079	.231	4.151	.000	.452	2.076
Leader Boards	.325	.051	.267	4.147	.000	.324	2.812
Rewards	-.020	.034	-.005	-.320	.502	.643	1.486
Progress Bars	.536	.067	.490	9.071	.000	.465	1.741
Trivia	.449	.078	.370	8.181	.000	.575	1.627
Opinion polls	.516	.095	.399	8.189	.000	.535	1.597
Mini-Games	.537	.049	.479	9.174	.000	.455	1.977

Source: Survey Data

Table 3.b showcases the coefficients for a variety of variables and their correlations with customer experience. The unstandardized coefficients for badges (-.078) and rewards (-.020) are negative, suggesting a negative impact on customer experience. Conversely, points (.219), leaderboards (.325), progress bars (.536), trivia (.449), opinion polls (.516), and mini-games (.537) exhibit positive

unstandardized coefficients, indicating a positive correlation with customer experience. The p-values for points, leader boards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games are all 0.000, which suggests they significantly influence customer experience. However, badges and rewards, with high significant values of 0.502 and 0.116 respectively, appear to have no effect on customer experience. The tolerance values for all the predicted variables range between 0.275 and 0.643, which suggests that multicollinearity does not affect the outcomes. Moreover, the VIF values for all the variables are between 1 and 10, which further supports the absence of multicollinearity. Therefore, it can be concluded that all gamification variables are statistically independent of each other, not causing inflation in the variability of the other predictors.

9. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION :

The study's findings imply that gamification plays a substantial role in enhancing customer experience, especially in today's increasingly competitive and dynamic work environment. The results affirm the premise that gamification significantly impacts the customer experience among banking customers in different private-sector banks. The detailed results and interpretations of the Correlation Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis tests can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Testing of Hypotheses

S. No.	Hypotheses	Test	Result
1	H1: The presence of badges is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
2	H2: The utilization of points is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
3	H3: The inclusion of leaderboards is significantly positively connected to customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
4	H4: Offering rewards is significantly positively correlated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
5	H5: The presence of progress bars is significantly positively related to customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
6	H6: Incorporating trivia activities is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
7	H7: The implementation of opinion polls is significantly positively linked to customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
8	H8: The inclusion of mini-games is significantly positively associated with customer experience in digital banking practices.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
9	H9: The application of gamification positively impacts on customer experience in digital banking practices.	Multiple Regression Analysis	H0 Accepted

Fig. 2: Final Accepted Conceptual Model

This study utilized Multiple Equation Analysis to test the relationships between several independent variables—badges, points, leaderboards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games—and a dependent variable, which is customer experience. Standardized regression weights were employed to articulate the relationships between these variables. The graphic illustration (Fig. 2) of these weights demonstrates that the eight identified gamification variables account for 34.1% of the variation in customer experience.

10. ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL DEVELOPED :

Analyzing research results is a critical process that involves scrutinizing and interpreting gathered data or developed conceptual models. The analysis of the conceptual model constructed for this study is crucial for understanding its potential applicability to similar problems. Numerous analysis frameworks are utilized in academic research. These include the SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis (Aithal, A., et al. 2015 [33] & Frederick, D. P., et al. 2021 [34]), PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis (Ho, J. K. K. 2014 [35] & Song, J., et al. 2017 [36]), and the ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis (Aithal, A., et al. 2015 [37] & Aithal, P. S. 2016 [38]). The ABCD analysis framework is utilized in this context to detail the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the developed model (Aithal, P. S. 2017 [39], Aithal, P. S. et al. 2016 [40] & Aithal, P. S. et al. 2016 [41]). These aspects offer valuable insights into the model's effectiveness and potential areas of improvement from a stakeholder perspective.

10.1 ABCD Listing from Banking Customers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) Enhanced customer engagement: Gamification can support client maintenance by making the financial experience really captivating and charming.
- (2) User-friendly interface: Gamification can assist banks with separating themselves in an exceptionally cutthroat market, offering special encounters to their clients.
- (3) Personalized experiences: Gamification takes into account customization and personalization of banking administrations, upgrading individual client experience.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Increased customer loyalty: By making banking really captivating and fulfilling, gamification can cultivate more noteworthy customer loyalty.
- (2) Improved financial literacy: Gamification components, as tests and difficulties, can be utilized to teach clients about monetary items and improve their monetary education.
- (3) Incentivized behaviors: Clients might be boosted to take part in sure monetary ways of behaving, such as saving or effective money management, using prizes and identifications.

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Technological barriers: Not all clients might have the important specialized abilities or admittance to partake in gamified banking encounters.
- (2) Security concerns: With additional intuitive advanced stages come expanded dangers and potential weaknesses that could prompt security breaks or misrepresentation.
- (3) Implementation costs: The expense of carrying out and keeping up with gamification components could be a limitation for certain banks.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) Overemphasis on rewards: Overreliance on remunerations might actually sabotage natural inspiration and lead to gamified components being viewed as manipulative or nosy.
- (2) Gamification fatigue: Clients might get exhausted or overpowered assuming similar gamification procedures are utilized drearily.
- (3) Misaligned incentives: While possibly not painstakingly planned, gamification could boost ways of behaving that are not to the greatest advantage of the clients or the banks.

10.2 ABCD Listing from Banking Service Providers' Points of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) Enhanced customer retention: Gamification can help client maintenance by making the financial experience seriously captivating and agreeable.
- (2) Differentiation in a competitive market: Gamification can assist banks with separating themselves in a profoundly cutthroat market, offering extraordinary encounters to their clients.
- (3) Increased data collection: Gamified collaborations can give significant information on client conduct and inclinations, empowering more customized administrations.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Increased usage of digital platforms: Gamification can empower more far reaching utilization of computerized financial stages, expanding functional proficiency and lessening costs.
- (2) Enhanced brand image: Gamification can add to a more current, client cordial picture, drawing in a more youthful segment.
- (3) Opportunity for cross-selling and up-selling: Customized rewards and difficulties can be utilized to elevate extra administrations to clients.

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Implementation and maintenance costs: Creating, carrying out, and keeping up with gamification highlights can be exorbitant and tedious.

(2) Technological constraints: There might be innovative impediments in carrying out cutting edge gamification highlights, especially for more modest or less carefully mature banks.

(3) Regulatory compliance: Banks need to guarantee that any gamified components follow pertinent guidelines and don't delude clients.

(D) Disadvantages:

(1) Potential for customer disillusionment: On the off chance that gamification is seen as manipulative or meddlesome, it could prompt client disappointment and damage the bank's standing.

(2) Risk of distracting from core services: There's a gamble that an extreme spotlight on gamification could occupy banks from their center administrations and capabilities.

(3) Short-term focus: While gamification can drive prompt commitment, there's a gamble of zeroing in a lot on momentary measurements to the detriment of long haul consumer loyalty and reliability.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS & SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH :

In light of the findings from the study, a few suggestions can be proposed for banking specialist co-ops. It, first and foremost, is pivotal to tailor gamification components to line up with individual client ways of behaving and inclinations, making the financial experience more private and locking in. Standard updates and enhancements of the gamified highlights could assist with keeping the client experience new and stay away from gamification weaknesses. Also, banks could use gamified components as an instructive device to work on clients' monetary education, assisting them with pursuing informed monetary choices. While compensating clients, an equilibrium should be struck to guarantee the experience isn't exclusively about pursuing prizes, yet additionally about working with positive monetary ways of behaving. In conclusion, as banks carry out more gamified components, they should at the same time reinforce their safety efforts to shield client information and guarantee secure exchanges.

The study opens up an abundance of chances for additional investigation and examination. For example, studies could be led to figure out the drawn-out effect of gamification on client dependability and the general productivity of banks. Examinations could likewise dig into segment-based examinations to comprehend how different age gatherings, sexes, or pay levels answer gamification in computerized banking. Near investigations could be done to gauge the viability of various gamification techniques across various banks, districts, or even nations. Moreover, future research could also analyze the impact of individual gamification elements such as points, badges, leader boards, etc., on customer engagement and satisfaction. One more encouraging region for future examination could be concentrating on the effect of gamification on clients' monetary ways of behaving, like saving propensities or speculation ways of behaving. This would offer a more profound comprehension of how gamification can be utilized to draw in clients as well as to encourage monetarily sound ways of behaving.

12. CONCLUSION :

The examination has presented shrewd findings. The review showed the way that gamification could assume a critical part in improving client experience, cultivating client commitment, and encouraging a feeling of seriousness and achievement through different components like badges, points, leaderboards, rewards, progress bars, trivia, opinion polls, and mini-games. The review's outcomes have revealed insight into the capability of gamification as an essential device in computerized banking to change routine monetary exchanges into more charming, intelligent, and vivid encounters. Besides, it likewise demonstrates that a very much planned gamified banking experience can bring about better client reliability and fulfillment, consequently adding to the seriousness of banks in the developing computerized financial scene. Nonetheless, the concentrate additionally accentuates the significance of cautious and vital execution of gamification strategies, considering the different necessities and inclinations of clients and the quickly changing innovative scene. It recommends that the fruitful coordination of gamification in computerized banking isn't simply about consolidating game mechanics, however, about making significant and drawing in encounters that enhance clients' financial connections. Generally, the review highlights the capability of gamification in reclassifying client experience in computerized financial practices and offers a venturing stone for future examination in this thrilling and developing field.

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